

The Role of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in Governance and National-Level Policy Processes in Bo City, Sierra Leone

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Abstract

This research investigated the role of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in governance and national-level policy processes in Bo City, Sierra Leone. The study highlighted the significance of CSOs in promoting democratic governance, fostering civic participation, and influencing public policy development at both local and national levels. Bo City, as a hub for civic engagement in Sierra Leone, provides a critical case for understanding how CSOs interact with government institutions, advocate for citizens' rights, and contribute to the formulation and implementation of policies.

A randomized sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample of every stratum contributing to national development in Bo City the sample size was determined. By using appropriate statistical data to ensure the adequate representation of multi-sectorial stakeholders.

The research begins by situating CSOs within the broader framework of governance and policy processes in Sierra Leone. It examined the historical evolution of CSOs in the country, their foundational principles, and how their role has evolved over time in response to political, social, and economic changes. Sierra Leone's post-conflict recovery, democratic transition, and decentralized governance reforms have created a conducive environment for CSOs to engage with the state and other stakeholders in policy dialogue. Bo City, being the second-largest city, reflects the dynamics of civil society activism outside the capital Freetown, offering insights into how grassroots organizations influence governance in non-urban centers.

The specific objectives of the research are to examine the role of empowered CSOs in enhancing good governance and policy processes in Bo City, to identify the key factors influencing the sustainability of CSOs capacity building initiatives in Bo City, and to provide recommendations to local councils, MDAs, CSOs, and development partners. The ways in which CSOs in Bo City participate in governance and policy formulation, the challenges they face, and their strategies for overcoming these obstacles. It focuses on three key areas of CSO engagement: advocacy for good governance, public policy development, and accountability mechanisms. CSOs in Bo City are instrumental in shaping governance structures by holding local government authorities accountable, monitoring service delivery, and promoting transparency in resource allocation. Their role extends to raising awareness among the population about their civic rights and responsibilities, fostering citizen participation in the democratic process, and providing platforms for marginalized groups to voice their concerns.

The research concludes that strengthening the capacity of CSOs in Bo City is essential for enhancing their role in governance and policy processes. It recommends that both the government and development partners provide technical and financial support to CSOs to enable them to contribute more effectively to national-level policy dialogues. Additionally, fostering greater collaboration between CSOs, local government, and other stakeholders is crucial for creating more inclusive and responsive governance systems in Bo City and Sierra Leone as a whole.

Key Words: Civil Society Organizations, governance, policy

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Civil society Organizations are recognized as key actors in democratization processes worldwide. CSOs act as intermediaries between the state and citizens, advocating for policy reforms, monitoring government actions, and providing services where public institutions are lacking. Capacity building initiatives by external donors, such as the European Union, are designed to strengthen CSOs by improving their organizational capabilities, technical skills, and advocacy strategies. Governance is an issue of concern all over the world. It has become very important that people participate in the governance processes of a country. In most developing countries, especially in Sierra Leone, it was not a common practice to discuss governance issues, but the past two decades have shown a growing need for people to participate in governance processes, Johns (1999).

In Bo City, the role played by CSOs to consolidating good governance has been significant, and have triggered local governance structure in the city. Civil society and its role in promoting good governance have garnered significant attention in the context of Bo City evolving political and socio-economic landscape. The role of Civil Society Organizations in Governance and National Level Policy Processes is a topic of immense significance and it requires further exploration. In this research, Local Councils, Ministries, Department and Agencies, NGOs, EU project interns, and the stakeholders of the community of this study; engulfed with examining the role of empowered CSOs in enhancing good governance and policy processes in Bo City; with assessing the effectiveness of the European Union funded capacity building initiative on CSOs in Bo City; coupled with the identification of the key factors influencing the sustainability of CSOs capacity building efforts in Bo City. The study also provides an analysis of recommendations that informs MDAs, local councils, civil society organizations, development partners in enhancing civil society organizations participation in governance and national level policy processes in Bo City and similar context.

The study also examines the role of civil society organizations in governance, and policy processes in Bo City. It also underscores how the participation of CSOs in governance contributes to peace and development strides in the region leading to social justice, transparency and accountability in the governance space in the region.

Furthermore, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the role of empowered CSOs in enhancing good governance and policy processes in Bo City. By identifying the key factors influencing the sustainability of civil society capacity building efforts, its impacts on governance process, and possible solutions, this review will contribute to the ongoing debate on this issue, and give insight to CSOs, local councils, development partners, NGOs, MDAs and other stakeholders in Bo City and beyond.

Many African governments viewed civil society organizations as a threat to their power and often use repressive tactics to silence dissenting voices. Governments in Africa often use a range of repressive tactics to intimidate civil society organizations and activists, including arrests, detention without trial, torture, harassment, and even extrajudicial killings. They also impose restrictions on the activities of civil society organizations, such as limiting their ability to operate, banning them from certain activities, and denying them access to funding and resources. Another tactic used by some African governments is the manipulation of legal frameworks to restrict civil society activities. For example, laws regulating NGOs can be used to limit their activities, while restrictive media laws can be used to prevent the media from reporting on issues that the government deems sensitive or critical. The impact of government repression and intimidation on civil society can be devastating. It stifles free expression, discourages dissent, and undermines efforts to promote good governance and human rights. It also erodes trust in government institutions and undermines the rule of law, which are essential for democracy and good governance (Mlambo et al, 2019).

Informal civil society organizations have been part of Sierra Leone, even before colonization. There existed such community-based organizations as the Poro and the Bondo (traditional secret societies for men and women, respectively). In certain communities, the Poro was the basis for local Governance. These CSOs however, were not only exclusive but also essentially selfish in the pursuance of their respective interests and fragmented. Many aspects of civil society are discernible from the various regimes that have been in

power since independence in 1961. The basic question is whether there was any tendency toward the development of civil society during the existence of the following regimes? (i.e. 1961 – 1967 the regime of the Sierra Leone Peoples Party under Sir Albert; the National Redemption Council (NRC) 1968-1985, the All Peoples Congress (APC) under Dr. Siaka P. Stevens; 1985 – 1992 the APC regime under Dr. Joseph Saidu Momoh; 1992 – 1996 National Provisional Ruling Council (NPRC) under Captain Valentine Strasser; 1995 – May 25 1997; under Alhaji Dr. Ahmed Tejan Kabbah, SLPP Government, May 1997 – 1998 February; the Armed Forces Revolutionary Council (AFRC) under Colonel Johnny Paul Koroma; 1998 to date the SLPP Government of Alhaji Dr. Ahmed Tejan Kabbah.)

A critical evaluation of the already mentioned periods and regimes will show that the development of civil society was not the same in all the regimes, while some demonstrated tolerance, others rejected tolerance, and even discouraged the development of civil society movements in Sierra Leone. During the rule of the SLPP under Sir Albert Margai (1964 – 1967) civil society groups like the Bar Association, the Academic Staff of the University of Sierra Leone, the National Union of Students spoke out against Sir Albert Margai's proposal to make Sierra Leone a One Party State.

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

In recent years, there has been so many problems and issues that limited the effectiveness of the role civil society organizations play in enhancing capacity building and fostering development through inclusive participation in governance and national level policy processes. In Africa, and specifically in Sierra Leone, CSOs face numerous problems and challenges that hamper their effectiveness. This research delves into these challenges, highlighting how they impede the ability of CSOs to contribute effectively to national development. CSOs often operate in restrictive regulatory environments that limit their activities. In some African countries, governments impose stringent regulations on registration, funding, and operations of CSOs.

These legal constraints can be particularly burdensome in Sierra Leone, where bureaucratic red tape and lack of clarity in the legal framework hinder the establishment and functioning of CSOs, the fear of government interference or reprisal can deter CSOs from engaging in critical advocacy and accountability roles. Political interference is another major obstacle for CSOs. Governments in many African countries, including Sierra Leone, many view CSOs as threats to their authority and seek to undermine their activities. This can take the form of harassment, intimidation, and even outright repression. For instance, CSO leaders and activists may face arrests, threats, and violence for speaking out against government policies or corruption. Such a hostile environment stifles the ability of CSOs to operate freely and advocate effectively for social change.

Many CSOs in Sierra Leone and Bo City by extension, struggle with capacity and skill gaps. These organizations often lack the necessary human resources, expertise, and technical skills to design, implement, and monitor development programs effectively. This deficiency can be attributed to inadequate training, limited access to professional development opportunities, and high staff turnover due to low salaries and job insecurity. Without sufficient capacity, CSOs find it challenging to deliver impactful and sustainable development initiatives. Effective coordination and collaboration among CSOs are essential for maximizing their impact. However, in Sierra Leone, there is often a lack of coordination among CSOs, leading to duplication of efforts and inefficient use of resources. This problem is exacerbated by competition for funding, which can create an environment of mistrust and reluctance to share information or collaborate on joint initiatives. Enhancing coordination mechanisms and fostering a culture of collaboration are crucial for improving the effectiveness of CSOs. Access to accurate and timely information is vital for the effectiveness of CSOs.

However, many organizations in Sierra Leone face significant challenges in this regard. Limited access to technology, unreliable internet connectivity, and a lack of information-sharing platforms hinder the ability of CSOs to gather data, conduct research, and disseminate information. This limitation affects their capacity to make informed decisions, advocate for evidence-based policies, and engage effectively with stakeholders. Social and cultural barriers is another problem that pose challenges for CSOs in Sierra Leone. Traditional

norms and values can sometimes conflict with the goals and activities of CSOs, particularly those advocating for gender equality, human rights, and social justice. In some communities like Bo City known for its diversity in cultural beliefs and significance is not exempted from these concerns, experiencing its share of reported incidents of resistance to change or skepticism towards CSOs, which can hinder their ability to mobilize support and implement programs effectively. Overcoming these barriers requires a deep understanding of local contexts and culturally sensitive approaches. The physical and infrastructural environment in Sierra Leone, presents additional hurdles for CSOs. Poor infrastructure, such as inadequate transportation networks and unreliable electricity, can significantly impede the implementation of development projects, particularly in remote and rural areas. Environmental challenges, such as climate change and natural disasters, further complicate the work of CSOs, as they must navigate these issues while trying to achieve their development goals.

Ensuring the sustainability and measuring the impact of development initiatives is a critical challenge for CSOs. Many organizations struggle to secure long-term funding and support, making it difficult to sustain their programs and initiatives over time. Moreover, there is often a lack of robust monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the effectiveness and impact of their work. Without reliable impact measurement, it is challenging for CSOs to demonstrate their value, attract funding, and scale up successful interventions. Trust and credibility are essential for the effectiveness of CSOs, but these can be eroded by various factors. Instances of corruption, mismanagement, and lack of transparency within some CSOs can undermine public confidence and support. Additionally, negative perceptions or skepticism about the motives and activities of CSOs can hinder their ability to engage communities and stakeholders. Building and maintaining trust and credibility require adherence to high standards of governance, transparency, and accountability.

However, while these multifaceted issues limit the effective functioning and inclusive participation of civil society organizations in governance have been widely documented, there is a dearth of research exploring the implications it has on advocating for rights, policy reformations, transparency and accountability to accelerate good governance in post-conflict Sierra Leone. Understanding the interplay between enhancing CSOs participation in governance and national level policy processes and the consolidation, rehabilitation and reconstruction of peace building processes is crucial to fostering accountability, rule of law, transparency, and maximizing the need to consolidate democratic values and principles to enhance the building of strong institutions that serves as a beacon for national development and societal stability.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

CSOs comprise non-governmental bodies, whose existence is established on the need to complement government effort on various issues that affect a country. Thomson (2010) argues that in any democratic society, civil society bodies are key elements in the governance process of a country. Democracy in its own reflection, to flourish will require various bodies to make an input in the governance process of the country. Thus, the existence of the CSOs is drawn from the premise to be an input to issues affecting the society. With the participation of CSOs in the governance process, governments are complemented in ensuring that all challenges of society are dealt with in a manner befitting the standards of a state.

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) needs to recognize how they can engage with policy processes more effectively. CSOs establish pressure groups and mobilize resources to form more supporters in policy engagement. But in the real world, CSOs are often financially unstable, have weak capacity and are poorly connected in policy process. The active involvement of CSOs in policy decisions will always benefit the public and the poor. It has been so challenging for CSOs to maximize their influences in policy decisions for the interest of the public. As for this literature review on the part of CSOs, the following papers by Jolie Court (2005& 2006) will give guidance on the subject matter.

Julie (2005) present Global facts that if CSOs are well established and supported them can always be of greater influence in policy decisions. Julie provides an example showing how CSOs in Ghana, Zimbabwe and Kenya which by then was providing 40% of all healthcare and education services in those countries. In Bangladesh alone there was an estimated 22,000 development NGOs which provide some service (credit,

health or education) to between 25-30% of the population. According to Julie (2005) NGOs managed to reach 20% of the world's poorest in those times with only annual global revenues of some US\$12 billion.

However, for the last 15 years, the capacity of CSOs to effectively engage in policy process has been limited by poor resources, sustainability, political pressures and capacity in policy process which inhibited their scope to effectively influence policy decisions. The findings of the survey by Julie (2005) indicate that CSOs are now much informed that policy engagement can often have a greater impact with widespread benefits than contestation and their service delivery effort alone. The global situation indicates that CSOs are often failing to influence policy processes in developing countries than developed countries. Among many other factors, political challenges, poor capacity, and lack of evidence in policy engagement were mentioned by Julie (2005) to be factors undermining the credibility and effectiveness of CSOs to influence policy decisions in developing countries. It has been elucidated that CSOs in developing countries like Sierra Leone and Bo City ignore research findings during policy engagement.

Julie (2005) emphasizes that, for effective CSOs involvement in policy decisions or seeking to influence policy it is vital for CSOs to understand the institutions and actors involved in policy processes, both on a formal and informal level. Doing so helps to recognize the incentives and pressures on those involved, as well as the type of evidence and communication approach needed to maximize the chances of policy influence.

Maitra (2003); researched on the role of civil society in democratization in Zambia and argued that Democratization process in Zambia has been considered by most as a success story. The electoral defeat of the United National Independence Party (UNIP) under the leadership of Kenneth Kaunda after twenty-seven years of rule in 1991 and the abolition of the one-party state was primarily instigated by mass-based popular movements. The subsequent multi-party elections on 31st October 1991 ushered the regime of another political party the "Movement for Multi-Party Democracy" (MMD) under the leadership of Late President Frederick Titus Chiluba and led to peaceful change of government. Maitra argues that in the light of the democratic election of President Rupiah Banda, the existence of an alert and strong civil society would remain crucial for Zambia. It would be imperative to keep in mind the lessons learnt from the mass movement of the 1990s, against the regime of Kenneth Kaunda and the 2011 elections that ushered in yet another regime of the Patriotic Front (PF) under the leadership of President Michael Chilufya Sata, MHSRIP.

Juan (2010); argues that CSOs remain an avenue through which African countries can fight the wars that have hampered proper governance on the continent. A vibrant civil society therefore is one that is most needed and not one that is dormant. Civil Society institutions exist not for the role they are able to perform but to the expectations of the people. Juan (2010), noted that some CSOs are however, very much compromised that they would serve no purpose in the governance process of a country. When CSOs becomes compromised they tend not to differentiate what is good and what is bad, usually in most cases they tend to fix those in leadership for their own benefits. In other instances, they just exist to frustrate the activities of government by engaging in activities that are bent on derailing government in implementing its programs. Panny (2011); also notes that the existence of the civil society movement should not be centered on only opposing the government but on the desire to help government implement its programs as this is the only way meaningful development can be achieved. The Civil Society in such an environment becomes a key stakeholder in national agenda. Since civil society is a key stakeholder, it has influence on the constitution and the implementation of government programs in order to meet its objectives.

Pantrice (2008), highlighted on the reasons civil society movements have been rising at a rapid rate. According to his findings, the rise in the civil society activities was as a result of the need to balance power. The Civil Society Organizations have the right to participate in issues that affect them. In Africa and in most countries where governments are opposed to the rise in the activities of the Civil Society have been because of the fear that their activities have the potential of bringing down the government. Oswalds (1996); observes that in developed countries, however, the activities of the CSOs are highly respected. Governments

have nothing to fear and there is no need for them to clamp at the activities of the civil society movement. In Africa where the activities of the Civil Society movements are restricted it has been because of leaders themselves that feel that CSOs are not bodies that should even take part in the governance process of the country. A report by the United Nations (2011) indicated rampant abrogation of the rights of most CSOs in Africa. Billy (2010); observed from his research that there was too much corruption in Africa that African leaders had no interest in having a CSO that will always expose their corrupt activities. He says corruption in Africa has become a cancer that African leaders amass colossal wealth which is not rightfully earned. They will always want to sweep the dirt below the black carpet where they are not questioned on what they do. Edelman (2012); highlighted on the mistrust between Government and the Civil society organization, he says trust in government suffers a severe breakdown across the globe and says it is a shame to see some governments quietly gagging their civil society actors. Martinez (2012), strongly believes that governments and their citizens have so much to gain from a strong and dynamic CSO if the relationship is built on trust. Civil society plays an important role of complementing the role of government in the enhancement of good governance and democratization. The independence struggles of many African countries cannot be complete without mentioning the role of civil society of advancing civic education and raising peoples' awareness on governance issues in the country.

While the literature by Julie (2005), discusses the influence of CSOs and their reach, it did not provide a long-term impact assessment. How sustainable the outcomes of these services are, what are the long-term effects on the communities served by these CSOs, the literature provides examples from specific countries, but it lacks a broader comparative analysis across different regions or continents. How do CSOs' effectiveness and strategies differ in various socio-political contexts, the literature mentions that well-established CSOs can influence policy decisions, but it did not delve deeply into the dynamics of this interaction. In this review, the study aims to uncover the existing barriers that limits CSOs in policy engagements and service delivery that will influence local governance policy decisions in developing countries like Sierra Leone.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A randomized sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample of every stratum contributing to national development in Bo City in order to conduct surveys. The sample size was determined by using appropriate statistical data to ensure the adequate representation of multi-sectorial stakeholders.

Purposive sampling was used to select key stakeholders including Local councils, MDAs, and representatives from relevant civil organizations involved in governance and national level policy processes to conduct interviews and focus group discussions. This selection was based on their knowledge, expertise, and experiences related to governance and national level policy processes in Bo City.

4.0 DATA DISCUSSION

Table 1: Responses of how can CSOs influence policy making at local level

Variable	Frequency	Percentage%
Yes	72	79
No	19	21
Total	91	100

In accordance with the data shown above in Table 1, with 72 respondents representing 79% of the target population, believes that CSOs influence policy making at local level and 19 respondents representing 21% do not believe that CSOs can influence policy making at local level. This data suggests that a strong majority of respondents believe that Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) can influence policy-making at the local level. This majority view highlights the perceived power and potential of CSOs in shaping public policies. CSOs often advocate for the needs of marginalized or underrepresented communities, providing a voice that can bridge the gap between citizens and government officials. Their ability to engage the public, and mobilize communities to demand accountability from local governments can be instrumental in shaping decisions that reflect the public's needs and interests.

For CSOs to influence policy-making, they can engage in several key activities. First, they can act as mediators between citizens and local governments by organizing public consultations and encouraging community participation in governance processes. Second, they can conduct research and provide evidence-based recommendations to policymakers, helping to inform and shape decisions with relevant data. Third, CSOs often build networks and coalitions, amplifying their voices and increasing their capacity to influence policies through collective action. By engaging in advocacy campaigns, participating in policy forums, and fostering partnerships with local authorities, CSOs can effectively shape the development and implementation of local level policies.

The chart indicates the responses from participants in this study about if there is adequate recognition and support for the role of CSOs in governance. 37 respondents which represents 41% of the targeted research population agreed that Yes, there is an adequate recognition and support for the role of CSOs in governance. And 54 respondents which represents 59% of the study population disagreed that there is no adequate recognition and support for the role of CSOs in governance.

How do you think CSOs can effectively contribute to improving governance at the local level?

The chart above indicates the responses of participants to how CSOs can effectively contribute to improving governance at local level. 73 respondents which represents 80% of the target population in this study confirmed that CSOs can effectively contribute to governance through partnership and collaboration. Whilst 18 respondents which represents 20% of the research population confirmed that CSOs can effectively contribute to improving governance at local level when they work alone. There were no responses to blackmailing and propaganda, which represents 0% of the study population.

How can government bodies and CSOs work together more effectively for better governance outcomes?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage%
To collaborate in development activities	71	78
To politicize CSOs	18	20
To criticize every government activity	2	2
Monopoly	0	0
Total	91	100

In table 2 above, shows data from the responses of participants to the research question: How can government bodies and CSOs work together more effectively for better governance outcomes?

71 respondents which represents 78% of the research population believes that in order for government bodies and CSOs to work together for better governance outcomes, both CSOs and government need to collaborate in development activities. 18 respondents, which represents 20% of the targeted population believe that politicizing CSOs can create an environment where both CSOs and government bodies work more together for better governance outcomes. Whilst 2 respondents that represent 2% of the population believes that criticizing every government activity can allow CSOs and government bodies to work together more effectively for better governance outcomes.

Table 3: What strategies do you think could be implemented to further strengthen the role of CSOs in governance and policy processes?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage%
CSOs need to form a network and coalition for collaboration	48	53
Capacity building projects, monitoring government activities and provision of necessary funding for CSOs activities	32	35
Recognition of CSOs influence in governance	11	12
Total	91	100

The data as shown in the table above suggests several strategies which respondents believed it to strengthen the role of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in governance and policy processes. 48 respondents, representing 53% of the research population emphasized the importance of collaboration by forming networks and coalitions *“CSOs need to form a network and coalition for collaboration, it can help them more”*. This approach could enhance collective influence, allowing CSOs to pool resources, share knowledge, and coordinate actions more effectively, increasing their impact on policy decisions. While 32 respondents, representing 35% of the study population emphasized for *“Capacity building projects, monitoring government activities and provision of necessary funding for CSOs activities”*, these responses highlight the need for capacity building, monitoring, and sufficient funding. By investing in training and developing CSOs' skills, they can become more adept at navigating governance structures and implementing their initiatives. Additionally, effective monitoring and evaluation can ensure accountability and showcase the effectiveness of CSO activities. And 11 respondents, representing 12% of the study population emphasized on the recognition of CSOs influence in governance *“Recognition of CSOs influence in governance”*. This suggests the need for institutional recognition, which could lead to more formalized roles for CSOs within governance frameworks, allowing them greater access to decision-making platforms. Together, these strategies collaboration, capacity building, funding, and formal recognition could significantly enhance the role of CSOs in governance and policy processes in Bo City as the research community and similar context.

Table 4: Responses to how can CSOs ensure transparency and accountability with government

Variables	Frequency	Percentage%
Serve as watchdog	76	84
To receive bribe	9	9
To be deceptive	0	0
To be divided	6	7
Total	91	100

In accordance with the data showing in Table 4 above, 76 respondents representing 84% of the study population confirmed that CSOs can ensure transparency and accountability in their engagements with government by serving as a watchdog, whereas 9 respondents representing 9% believes CSOs ensure

transparency and accountability with government by receiving bribe, 6 respondents representing 7% believes that been divided is how CSOs

5.0 Summary of Findings

This study was undertaken to understand “The Role of CSOs in Governance and National Level Policy Processes in Bo City”, with the aim of providing insight into governance practices and policy processes with the promotion of development and harmony within the community. The study revealed that CSOs role in governance has a significant impact on the trust and relationships between the CSOs, Local Councils, MDAs and the community. The study also found that the CSOs can foster initiatives of development and can engage government and local councils on policy decisions that will enhance effective and efficient service delivery. It is evident that addressing the challenges CSOs face is crucial for good governance and better policy process outcomes in Bo City. The study highlighted the need for strengthened advocacy, partnership, and collaboration in order to efficient service delivery. This study recommended adequate capacity building training for CSOs, Local councils and MDAs, stricter accountability measures, and increased advocacy drives to rebuild trust and relationships.

Overall, the findings of the study underscored the detrimental impact of the ineffectiveness of CSOs in governance and policy processes in Bo City. Addressing these issues is crucial in fostering a developed and stable society.

Examine the role of empowered CSOs in enhancing good governance and policy processes in Bo City

The findings for this study shows that CSOs are key actors in promoting good governance practices. Findings from the study confirmed that among the various roles played by CSOs in ensuring good governance and policy processes is serving as a watchdog to hold government accountable to its activities in service delivery. These findings from the study can better ensure effective service delivery and further promotes trust and accountability in governance and policy issues. The data presented highlights a significant perception among respondents regarding the role of Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in influencing local-level policy-making. Of the 91 respondents, 72, representing 79% of the target population, believe that CSOs can impact the decision-making process at the local level. This high percentage suggests that the majority of the population views CSOs as important actors in shaping policies that affect their communities. Such findings point to a general trust in the advocacy and participatory roles that CSOs play, indicating that they are seen as effective channels for representing community interests and pushing for policy changes.

In contrast, a smaller proportion, 19 respondents or 21%, do not believe that CSOs influence local policy-making. This group may reflect skepticism toward the effectiveness or visibility of CSO efforts in local governance, possibly due to perceived limitations in resources, access to decision-makers, or past experiences of low impact. Despite this minority opinion, the overwhelming majority supports the idea that CSOs have the ability to affect policy outcomes, reinforcing the view that these organizations remain vital for participatory governance and citizen engagement at the local level.

To identify the key factors influencing the sustainability of CSOs capacity-building efforts in Bo City

The research findings indicate that a significant portion of respondents identified multiple challenges facing Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in Bo City, with the majority of 55 respondents (61% of the study population) perceiving a combination of issues lack of access to funding opportunities, lack of partnerships, and government oppression as the primary hurdles to effective participation in governance. This suggests that these challenges are interconnected and collectively undermine the ability of CSOs to contribute meaningfully to governance processes. The prevalence of this comprehensive view among respondents highlights the need for a multifaceted approach to addressing these barriers, as focusing on only one issue may not be sufficient to improve CSO engagement.

In addition to the majority view, specific challenges were highlighted by smaller groups of respondents. Lack of access to funding was identified by 15 respondents (16%), emphasizing financial constraints as a

significant obstacle to CSO activity. Meanwhile, 18 respondents (20%) pointed to the lack of partnerships, which could hinder collaboration and the sharing of resources, while only 3 respondents (3%) saw government oppression as a standalone challenge. The relatively low percentage citing government oppression could suggest that financial and collaborative barriers are more immediate concerns for CSOs, though government influence remains a factor. These findings underscore the complexity of issues faced by CSOs in Bo City, necessitating comprehensive interventions from both internal CSO strategies and external stakeholders.

The research findings reveal that a significant majority (79%) of the study population believes that civil society organizations (CSOs) encounter barriers to meaningful participation in governance and policy processes. This indicates a widespread perception among stakeholders that CSOs face challenges, which may include limited access to decision-making platforms, inadequate funding, political interference, or lack of capacity. These barriers potentially hinder the ability of CSOs to influence governance effectively, diminishing their role in representing marginalized groups, advocating for policy reforms, and ensuring transparency and accountability in government processes. The prevalence of this view suggests that addressing these barriers could be critical to improving governance outcomes and fostering more inclusive policy development.

However, the study also reveals that 21% of the respondents represented by 19 individuals believe that CSOs do not face such barriers. This minority perspective could indicate that some participants view the existing governance structures as relatively open or accessible to CSOs, or they may belong to organizations that have been successful in overcoming common barriers. This discrepancy between the majority and minority views points to a potential variation in experiences, possibly influenced by the type of CSO, its resources, or its level of engagement with the policy process.

6.0. Conclusion

From the findings of this research it is concluded that civil society organizations are key stakeholders in governance and the policy processes of the country. They play a critical role of ensuring government functions are within the stipulated guidelines of the constitution which is the supreme law of the land. Civil society organizations play a role in promoting and protecting democracy. Therefore, an active and flourishing civil society movement is important if national development and democracy is to be achieved. The reasons that are advanced to a flourishing civil society are many but what has been critical has been the respect to advocacy tenets where advocating for better policies is the main aspiration to good governance. This is mostly seen in developed countries where the role of civil society organizations is quite regarded because enough legislation exists that protects the civil society movement. In such countries, civil society organizations have a lot of influence and this has been attributed to a conducive environment that has and continues to be created.

The research findings also conclude that civil society movements in developing countries are undermined by those in authority, they are seen as an enemy that should be fought at all cost. In Bo City, the researcher found that successive governments have for example been trying to introduce legislation that is targeted at regulating the civil society landscape aimed at clamping on their roles rather than legislation that recognizes their roles in good governance processes of the country. Civil society organizations like NMJD, have been found to be critical of government on several issues that includes transparency and accountability, rule of law, human rights, gender based issues and the respect for the separation of powers which is in the spirit of good governance which the country has been striving to achieve. The study established that, though the Sierra Leonean government has made steady strides in democratization by embracing the civil society, the working environment remains generally not very conducive as there is mistrust between the civil society movement and the government.

7.0 Recommendations

Several investigative reports and recommendations have by been laid bare by different researchers and scholars on how civil society organizations roles can be enhanced in order that good governance remains the

aspirations of many societies. Notwithstanding such works and in view of the findings of this research work it is recommended that CSOs need to become stronger; above all more representative, and to acquire the capacity necessary for them to engage both popular bases and the state in policy formulation and analysis, unlike the current situation where its activities are more concentrated in the urban areas and largely characterized as an elite phenomenon. The researcher recommends however, the following:

Recommendation to Local Councils

- Form collaborative committees with representatives from both local councils and civil society organizations (CSOs) to identify and address key policy areas, ensuring diverse perspectives in decision-making.
- Create open communication platforms, such as regular forums or digital portals, to facilitate ongoing dialogue and feedback between local councils and CSOs, enhancing trust and accountability.
- Encourage co-design and co-implementation of policy initiatives by involving CSOs early in the process, leveraging their grassroots knowledge and expertise to improve the relevance and impact of policies.
- Offer training and resources to both local councils and CSOs to enhance their capacity for effective collaboration, ensuring both parties have the skills and knowledge needed for meaningful participation in governance processes.

Recommendation to MDAs

- MDAs should provide and create spaces for CSOs to monitor their activities in order to foster public trust and accountability.
- A coalition and network of MDAs and CSOs should be created to maximize the efficiency of MDAs in government service delivery.
- There should also be an access to information for CSOs to be able to determine the performance of MDAs and inform the public about progress and developments.

Recommendations to CSOs

- CSOs should continue to build internal capacity for them to be able to work and advocate efficiently on governance related policies.
- Let the advocacy strategies and cause be more about improving the standards for the masses. Advocacy should be more of the interest of the masses than CSOs interest.
- CSOs should also depoliticize their activities and remain neutral in governance and policy process issues.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

- Encourage inclusive dialogue where diverse voices, including marginalized groups, can participate in policy discussions and decision-making processes.
- Invest in building the capacity of CSOs through training, technical support, and sharing best practices.
- Provide consistent and long-term funding for CSOs, ensuring they have the necessary resources to engage in governance and policy work. Financial stability allows CSOs to remain independent and focused on advocating for good governance practices and holding institutions accountable.

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